

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D1.5

Ethics & Data Protection Policy

WP1 — T1.4 Ethics & Data Protection Policy

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¹PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Abstract

The PARC partnership has garnered attention and created expectations from the chemical risk assessment and management community. Policy-makers and the EU citizens are also taking notice of the partnership and are looking to see fruitful developments addressing their needs.

However, the PARC activities — covering many different fields of activities — must be designed and implemented in alignment with EU values and regulations to make sure that both needs and concerns are adequately addressed.

Ensuring that PARC duly take into account ethics concerns will only make the partnership outputs more valuable and facilitate the sustainable uptake of results by the different communities impacted by PARC.

This deliverable serves as a framework to guide PARC participants in the setting-up and implementation of their activities in line with the high ethics standards expected from PARC participants. It outlines the key values that should inform all activities and provides concrete support and information on the documents and processes that are expected.

Key Words

Ethics, personal Data, Data Management, Data Protection, DEPB, GDPR, Intellectual Property Rights, AI, process, animal experiments,

Table of contents

Document history _____	3
Abstract _____	4
Key Words _____	4
Table of contents _____	5
Authors and Acknowledgements _____	7
Acronyms _____	7
Glossary _____	8
Summary & background _____	9
Objectives of the PARC ethics framework _____	9
1. PARC ethics snapshot and structure _____	10
1.1 PARC ethics framework _____	10
1.2 Key ethics principles in PARC _____	13
1.2.1 General principles _____	13
1.2.1.1 Responsible Research and Innovation _____	13
1.2.2.2 Bioethics principles _____	14
1.2.2 Thematic principles _____	14
1.2.3.1 Human involvement _____	14
1.2.3.2 Data use and processing _____	15
1.2.3.3 Animal experimentation _____	16
1.2.3.4 Participation on non-EU countries _____	16
1.2.3.5 Artificial Intelligence _____	16
2. Ethics concerns identified _____	17
3. Ethics roles and responsibilities: ethics procedures _____	23
3.1 Overarching guideline _____	23
3.2 Thematic guidelines _____	25
3.2.1. Human involvement and informed consent _____	25
Informed Consent _____	25
3.2.2 Use of human cells/tissues _____	26
3.2.3 Data use and processing _____	27
3.2.3.1 Personal data: _____	27
3.2.3.2 Data reuse: _____	28
3.2.4. Animal experimentation _____	28
3.2.5. Involvement of non-EU countries _____	29

3.2.6. Environment, health and safety	30
3.2.7. Artificial intelligence	31
4. Conclusion	31
References	32
Annexes	37

Authors and Acknowledgements

The initial draft of the document has been prepared by the PARC Coordination Team (CT) with the support of the Task 1.4 co-leaders (Philippe Marin — EHESP; Lucija Perharic — NIJZ) and it has been refined with the valuable inputs and feedback from DEPB members (Célia Ventura — INSA; Sébastien Denys — SpF; Gilles Rivière — ANSES; Mirjam Luijten — RIVM; Iseult Lynch — UOB; Anni Lähdetie — PRH; Ineke Malsch — Malsch TechnoValuation; Lisbeth E. Knudsen — KU). Finally, it has been reviewed by the PARC Management Board (MB) to ensure that the processes and guidelines are suitable and feasible and that they can be disseminated to all participants.

Acronyms

List of abbreviations

Term	Abbreviation
Artificial Intelligence	AI
Replacement, Reduction and Refinement	3Rs
Consortium Agreement	CA
Conflict of Interest	CoI
Coordination Team	CT
Data and Ethics Protection Board	DEPB
Data Protection Officer	DPO
Declaration of Interest	DoI
Grant Agreement	GA
Governing Board	GB
General Data Protection Regulation	GDPR
Grant Signatory Board	GSB
Human biomonitoring for Europe	HBM4EU
International Board	IB
Management Board	MB
Material Transfer Agreement	MTA
New Approach Methodologies	NAMs
Next Generation Risk Assessment	NGRA
Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals	PARC
Principal Investigator	PI
Project Manager	PM
Risk Assessment	RA
Risk Management	RM
Stakeholder Forum	SF
Work Package	WP

Glossary

- Anonymised data:

Aggregated data merge information of multiple patients or survey participants and the collected information cannot be retraced to the individual data. Aggregated data are used in ecological studies and when analysing differences between countries or other population groups

- Activity:

Activity refers to the actions implemented in the framework of PARC. This includes all the work achieved in the PARC projects, but also in the transversal activities.

- Biobank:

A biobank is a collection of biological samples such as blood, urine and other tissues, often complemented with related information such as socio-economic position, diagnosed diseases etc. Biological samples stored in biobanks can be used in biomedical research and retrospective laboratory analysis to determine new biomarkers. Many countries in Europe have biobanks. These biobanks can be specific for one study or hospital, or organization of joint biobanks for several instances.

- Biometric data:

Personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person.

- Genetic data:

Personal data relating to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of a natural person which give unique information about the physiology or the health of that natural person and which result, in particular, from an analysis of a biological sample from the natural person in question.

- Informed consent:

Informed Consent is the decision, which must be written, dated and signed, to take part in a clinical trial or a survey involving personal data related to health or behaviors, taken freely after being duly informed of its nature, significance, implications and risks and appropriately documented, by any person capable of giving consent or, where the person is not capable of giving consent, by his or her legal representative; if the person concerned is unable to write, oral consent in the presence of at least one witness may be given in exceptional cases, as provided for in national legislation.

- Participant:

There are two types of participants in PARC activities:

First there are PARC actors, which comprises (i) internal partners (ie. from PARC participating organisations (ex: WP co-leaders, researchers involved in PARC projects)) and (ii) external partner (ie. which are not part of a PARC participating organisation, but are still involved in the PARC governance process (governing bodies or advisory bodies; ex: GB, SF,)).

Second, there is the volunteers, which are part of neither a PARC participating organisation, nor formally involved in PARCy (ie. GB, SF, IB).

- Personal Data:

Personal data is any information that relates to an identified or identifiable living individual. Different pieces of information, which collected together can lead to the identification of a particular person, also constitute personal data.

Personal data that has been de-identified, encrypted or pseudonymised but can be used to re-identify a person remains personal data and falls within the scope of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Personal data that has been rendered anonymous in such a way that the individual is not or no longer identifiable is no longer considered personal data. For data to be truly anonymised, the anonymisation must be irreversible.

- Processing (data):

Any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction. ssing:

Summary & background

The Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) is set up to consolidate and strengthen European public R&I capacities in chemical Risk Assessment (RA) to protect human health and the environment.

Building on lessons and knowledge learned from previous initiatives, notably the European Joint Programme HBM4EU¹ “Human biomonitoring for Europe”, PARC will establish an EU-wide Research and Innovation Risk Assessment hub of excellence composed of chemical RA and Risk Management (RM) bodies to support chemical RA and RM authorities at the national and EU level.

PARC activities cover a wide scope and will have to deal with sensitive ethics issues that must be adequately addressed in line with the highest ethical standards expected for EU research projects. To that end, an ambitious ethics framework must be maintained throughout all the Partnership’s activities.

Duly addressing these issues will help foster trust and acknowledgement by the PARC stakeholders and EU civil society.

Objectives of the PARC ethics framework

This document is intended to build on and specify the legal and contractual obligations of PARC and PARC partners in order to offer clear and concrete guidelines and coherent processes to properly address ethic concerns.

The initial legal and contractual framework of PARC on which this document is based includes:

- The national and EU legal obligations relevant for the activities of PARC.

¹ HBM4EU project - Human biomonitoring for Europe website available [here](https://www.hbm4eu.eu/) (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>)

- The provisions of the Grant Agreement (GA), notably article 10.1 ‘non-EU participants’, article 12.1 ‘Conflict of interests’, article 14 ‘Ethics and Values’ and the annex 5 section ‘Ethics and research integrity’.
- The provision of the Consortium Agreement (CA), including article 4.5 ‘Ethics’ and 10.9 ‘Code of conduct’.

This deliverable sets up and outlines the ethics framework that will oversee the activities of PARC and help all PARC actors to be cognizant and mindful of ethical concerns. It will specify the main identified concerns and provide guidance and due processes to adequately address ethical issues.

The main intended audience of this document includes all PARC actors, from WP co-leaders to PARC researchers. Outside PARC, stakeholders can also benefit from this document as it provides clarity and transparency on how PARC plan to address ethics concerns, they are specifically interested in.

1. PARC ethics snapshot and structure

1.1 PARC ethics framework

Taking into account the need to address general ethics issues and comply with the legal and contractual requirements, PARC has been developed and set-up dedicated ethics structure and processes.

A general overview of the PARC governance is available on its website [here](#).

Task 1.4 ‘Setting the ethics framework’

Within the Work Package 1 ‘Coordination and management’, the Task 1.4 is designed to set-up collaborative and constructive processes to ensure the monitoring of the Partnership’s actions with regards to ethical considerations and ensure they are properly taken into account throughout their life cycle: from their conception to their implementation.

Task 1.4 is co-led by Lucija Perharic (NIJZ) and Philippe Marin (EHESP) and collaborate closely with the PARC CT.

Task 1.4 is at the crux of all ethics processes in PARC, including the preparation of ethics deliverables, reports and the organisation of the Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB) and is tasked with maintaining a permanent overview of the ethics issues in the partnership.

Data and Ethics Protection Board

The DEPB is designed to support the Governing Board (GB), the Grant Signatory Board (GSB) and the Management Board (MB) by providing an outside opinion and its expertise in all matters pertaining to ethics and data protection to facilitate a smooth management of the partnership. The DEPB can also alert the competent boards of any issues it identifies. The composition and organisation of the DEPB is described in the D10.1 ‘Setting-up of the DEPB’.

The DEPB is chaired by the task co-leaders of T1.4: Lucija Perharic (NIJZ) and Philippe Marin (EHESP)

In addition, members from within the consortium are part of the PARC DEPB. These are representatives from the Work Packages 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 of PARC who are involved in scientific and transversal activities of the partnership. Their inclusion within the DEPB helps ensure that the DEPB is aware of the activities implemented and to facilitate communication with project teams and researchers.

The members selected are Célia Ventura (INSA) for WP3, Sébastien Denys (SpF) for WP4, Gilles Rivière (ANSES) for WP5, Mirjam Luijten (RIVM) for WP6 and Iseult Lynch (UOB) for WP7. Inclusion of other WPs in the DEPB is open on a voluntary basis.

Finally, the DEPB is completed by the participation of three external advisors with relevant expertise. These were identified from a pool of candidates and selected based on their expertise and experience of relevance for PARC.

The three external advisors selected are Prof. Lisbeth E. Knudsen, Dr. Ineke Malsch and Dr. Anni Lähdetie.

Prof. Lisbeth E. Knudsen is professor in Toxicology at University of Copenhagen Denmark with experience of human biomonitoring and ethics and as chair of the Ethics task in HBM4EU. Prof. Lisbeth E. Knudsen also has experiences with 3R and animal studies as Board member for 10 years of the Danish 3R Centre.

Dr. Ineke Malsch is an expert on ethics and responsible research and innovation of nanotechnology and other emerging technologies that founded Malsch TechnoValuation and EthicSchool.

Dr. Anni Lähdetie is a Senior patent Examiner specialized in the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of bioprocess technology at the Chemical technology unit of the Finnish Patent and Registration Office (PRH).

Fig. 1 – Composition of the PARC DEPB

Ethics deliverables and milestones

To ensure a proper monitoring of ethics issues and the setting-up of ethics processes, PARC will produce a number of ethics deliverables. These are compiled in the table 1 below:

Table. 1– List of ethics Deliverables and Milestones

Due (D/M#)	date	Name of the Deliverable / Milestone Description of the Deliverable / Milestone	Status
DELIVERABLES			
D10.2	M1	OEI - Requirement No. 2 Ethics assessment report related to Annual Work Plan Year 1	Submitted
D10.3	M8	OEI - Requirement No. 3 Report on ethics aspects related to Annual Summary Reports Year 1 and Ethics assessment report related to Annual Work Plan Year 2	Submitted
D10.1	M9	OEI - Requirement No. 1 Appointment of a Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB) to monitor compliance, carry out regular control and audit, and produce an annual ethics report with external and independent members.	Submitted
D1.5	M12	Ethics & Data Protection Policy The PARC ethics and data protection framework will set out the collaborative processes to be implemented to ensure the monitoring of PARC's actions concerning ethical considerations. It will provide the PARC ethical principles and procedures and will be developed in parallel and in coordination with the Data Management Plan under WP7.	Pending
D10.4	M20	OEI - Requirement No. 5 Report on ethics aspects related to Annual Summary Reports Year 2 and ethics assessment report related to Annual Work Plan Year 3	Pending
D10.5	M32	OEI - Requirement No. 7 Report on ethics aspects related to Annual Summary Reports Year 3 and ethics assessment report related to Annual Work Plan Year 4	Pending
D1.13	M42	Update of the Ethics & Data Protection Policy The PARC ethics and data protection framework which sets out the collaborative processes to be implemented to ensure the monitoring of PARC's actions concerning ethical considerations will be updated at mid-term to take into account lessons learnt and experience.	Pending
D10.6	M44	OEI - Requirement No. 9 Report on ethics aspects related to Annual Summary Reports Year 4 and ethics assessment report related to Annual Work Plan Year 5	Pending

D10.7	M56	OEI - Requirement No. 11 Report on ethics aspects related to Annual Summary Reports Year 5 and ethics assessment report related to Annual Work Plan Year 6	Pending
D10.8	M68	OEI - Requirement No. 13 Report on ethics aspects related to Annual Summary Reports Year 6 and ethics assessment report related to Annual Work Plan Year 7	Pending
MILESTONES			
M1	M12	Establishment of Data and Ethics Protection Board and ethical principles Composition of the DEPB officially announced; ethical principles available to all partners	Partially achieved (DEPB constituted)

Of particular relevance is the submission of annual Ethics reports detailing all ethics issues analysed during the previous year combined with an assessment of potential ethics concerns in the activities of the upcoming year.

These reports are prepared by T1.4 and reviewed by the DEPB and the MB.

The collection of feedback from partners will be essential to accurately monitor and outline how ethics issues have been addressed or prevented in the past year. Likewise, the assessment of the potential issues will require inputs from involved participants.

All PARC projects have to appoint an ethics contact point which is tasked to include information on ethics in the yearly update of the project fiche. The project manager assumes this role by default if no specific individual is appointed internally. The list of the ethics contact points for each projects is available in the annex (annex 1).

1.2 Key ethics principles in PARC

As outlined, activities in the risk assessment of chemicals can face a multitude of ethics issues with their own specificities. It is not possible to identify, list and prepare contingencies for them all given the broad scope of PARC and taking into account the fact that unexpected issues may occur alongside the lifetime of the partnership.

Nevertheless, PARC has set out key ethics principles that should guide participants in formulating answers to ethics challenges encountered. This aims to provide guidelines that can be adapted to suit the particular needs and concerns of the ethics issues arising.

1.2.1 General principles

1.2.1.1 Responsible Research and Innovation

In line with the EU's Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention on Human Rights, all research activities should be respectful of the

- the principle of **proportionality**
- the right to **privacy**
- the right to the **protection of personal data**
- the right to **physical and mental integrity** of all persons
- the right to **equality** and **non-discrimination**
- high levels of **protection of the environment** and **human health**

1.2.2.2 Bioethics principles

Building on HBM4EU's experience, PARC will also enshrine and respect the "Conventional bioethical principles" in its activities pertaining to human health.

These are²:

Autonomy — meaning that individuals have a keener understanding of their own best interests;

"Beneficence" — meaning that there is an impetus to "do well" for people and society. All stakeholders must be considered;

"Nonmaleficence," — meaning that activities should "do no harm" to people;

"Justice" — meaning that PARC's benefits and costs should be fairly and equitably distributed across stakeholders;

To complement these, PARC will respect the four additional bioethical principles, outlined by Beauchamp and Walters³:

"Utility" — meaning that activities should achieve the most good for the greatest number of people;

"Fidelity" — meaning that controversies that are similar should be addressed in a consistent manner;

"Veracity" — meaning that decisions or policies should neither ignore established truths nor try to state beliefs as such;

"Confidentiality" — meaning that the right to privacy must be respected.

In addition to bioethics principles outlined above, PARC activities involving human participants must also ensure:

→ **"Respect"** for persons and for human dignity — this means making sure that no actions undertaken should degrade involved individuals' sense of self-worth due to inadequate treatment (and processing of results) from PARC actors.

1.2.2 Thematic principles

1.2.3.1 Human involvement

All humans involved in PARC activities must be treated with respect, and their rights respected.

For many PARC activities, human involvement is essential. PARC is committed to ensure that involved individuals are respected and that they can understand the implications and draw benefits from their participation.

To that end, the following principles should be applied to all PARC activities:

² Harrison, M: Applying bioethical principles to human biomonitoring Environmental Health 2008 7 (Suppl 1):S8

³ Beauchamp T, Walters L, (Eds): Contemporary Issues in Bioethics. 1994, Belmont, California: Wadsworth Publishing Company

→ **“Voluntary participation”** — This means that participation in PARC activities from external participants must be entirely on a voluntary basis (clearly documented) and that they do not feel pressured or coerced into giving consent. In addition, non-participation must not lead to discrimination and/or socioeconomic negative consequences (ex: loss of access to healthcare).

→ **“Informed consent”** — This means that PARC activities must ensure that external participants are informed of the goals, methods and implications of the action and any other information they consider relevant for their decision, so that they fully understand the information provided before deciding on whether to participate.

Please note that for the involvement of humans that are unable to provide consent (ex: children), the consent must be obtained from the parents/legally authorised representative and it must be ensured that they have sufficient information to enable them to provide this on behalf and in the best interests of the children. Whenever possible, the assent of the participants should be obtained in addition to the consent of the parents/legal representatives.

1.2.3.2 Data use and processing

To ensure a good management and processing of the data created and used in PARC in addition to facilitating the uptake by citizens and researchers, the consortium is committed to the FAIRification of data. Essentially this means that data should be **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable⁴.

→ **“Findable”** — this means that metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers;

→ **“Accessible”** — this means that individuals should be in a capacity to know where to access the data they search (and know whether this require authentication and authorization);

→ **“Interoperable”** — this means that data should be able to be integrated with other data and to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing;

→ **“Reusable”** — this means that metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.

In addition, data used, produced and processed under PARC activities must limit the negative impact on the individuals as much as possible. As such, data used in the framework of PARC should ensure:

→ **“Transparency”** — this means participants/data subjects must be made aware and consent to the processing of their data. Furthermore, they must be informed of their rights and the potential risks that the data processing may bring;

→ **“Accountability of the data processing”** — this means that information about the data processing operations and the contact details of the relevant Data Protection Officer (DPO) should be available.

→ **“Data quality”** — this means that data processed should be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the activity; data reuse is possible provided that informed consent has been given and that the data in question is relevant for the follow-up research under consideration.

⁴ Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, & all: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data. 2016. Scientific Data

→ **“Data confidentiality”** — this means the level of data security must be appropriate to the risks for the participants/data subjects in case of unauthorized access or disclosure, accidental deletion or destruction of the data.

1.2.3.3 Animal experimentation

PARC activities should include the use of animal experimentation in a limited number of projects.

To ensure that the welfare of animals involved is respected and that animal experimentation is only used when it is necessary and duly justified, PARC is committed to respect and apply the ‘3Rs’ principles (**R**eplacement, **R**eduction, **R**efinement).

→ **“Replacement”** — this means replacing animal use by an alternative method or testing strategy (without use of live animals) as much as possible;

→ **“Reduction”** — this means reducing the number of animals used in the research activities;

→ **“Refinement”** — this means improving the breeding, accommodation and care of animals and the methods used to minimise pain, suffering, distress or lasting harm to animals.

1.2.3.4 Participation on non-EU countries

Some PARC partners come from non-EU countries. This means that they are not beholden to laws and standards of the EU regulations and this discrepancy may lead to ethics challenges.

To ensure that high ethical standards are respected in all PARC activities even those taking place in and/or involving non-EU-countries and participants, they should be legal in at least one EU member state.

It is important that PARC activities

→ **“Respect”** — this means that any use of local resources (especially animal and/or human tissue samples, genetic material, live animals) must be done with due consideration to cultural traditions of non-EU countries and participants involved.

→ **“Equality and fairness”** — this means that Non-EU countries and participants involved must be treated as equal, and benefits arising from PARC activities must be shared with local stakeholders, address local needs and aid local participants and their community.

To prevent ‘Ethics dumping’ when research partnerships are planned between high-income and lower-income settings, PARC activities should also be mindful of the ‘Global Code of Conduct for Equitable Research Partnerships’⁵.

1.2.3.5 Artificial Intelligence

The use of AI is increasingly common in research activities; however, it is not without ethical challenges that must be addressed.

As PARC activities do include the development of AI-based tools and resources, the partnership will follow the following principles:

⁵ ‘The TRUST Code - A Global Code of Conduct for Equitable Research Partnerships’ — available online (https://www.globalcodeofconduct.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/The_TRUST_Code.pdf).

→ **“Human agency and oversight”** — this means that AI systems must support human autonomy and decision-making, enabling users to make informed autonomous decisions regarding the AI systems.

→ **“Privacy and data governance”** — this means that AI systems must guarantee privacy and data protection throughout the system’s lifecycle.

→ **“Transparency”** — this means that all data sets and processes associated with AI decisions must be well communicated and appropriately documented.

→ **“Fairness, diversity and non-discrimination”** — this means that best possible efforts should be made to avoid unfair bias

→ **“Societal and environmental well-being”** — this means that the impact of the developed and/or used AI system/technique on the individual, society and environment must be carefully evaluated and any possible risk of harm must be avoided.

→ **Accountability** — this means that the actors involved in their development or operation should take responsibility for the way that these applications function and for the resulting consequences

2. Ethics concerns identified

RA of chemicals is a field which covers a wide scope of activities, domains and disciplines.

While some ethics concerns are common across WPs (ex: use of personal data, involvement of human participants, etc.), some activities pose unique ethics challenges and researchers must always keep in mind and consider potential issues to fine-tune their activities in line with ethical standards.

The table 2 below outlines the main ethics concerns identified (non-exhaustive list) in the following categories; Humans, use of human cells/tissues, data use and processing, animal experimentation, involvement of non-EU countries, environment, health and safety and artificial intelligence.

Within the WPs, each PARC project is required to complete a brief ethic self-assessment from its inception and update it yearly via the project fiches. This allows T1.4 and the DEPB to better monitor activities and ensure that specific ethics issues are adequately identified and addressed.

Table. 2 – Ethics concerns identified

Topic	WP	Concern identified	Answer
THEMATIC CONCERNS IDENTIFIED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION			
Humans	All	Involvement of human participants that are not part of PARC participating organisations during non-medical studies and activities. This notably includes workshops, meetings, trainings, surveys, feedback collection, etc.	Human participants in such activities will be duly informed of the objectives of the activities and will be able to make an informed choice on their participation. Participation will be on a voluntary basis
Humans	WP4, WP5, WP6,	Involvement of human participants in biomedical studies,	PARC will make sure that all participants are aware of the objectives of the studies, and

		including vulnerable individuals and children/minors, notably during the HBM studies and cohorts	that they opt-in through detailed Informed Consent procedures. For individuals that are not able to provide Informed consent (ex: children), the informed consent of legal representatives (parents/guardians) will be collected. Assent will be requested for minors aged 15-18 years. Ethics approval have to be collected prior to the start of the activity.
Humans	WP4, WP5, WP6	Activities including the collection of samples from human participants using invasive procedures	The procedures and their objectives will have to be justified and duly explained to human participants. This includes the specification of the types of human cells, tissues, biological matrices obtained. Informed consent from volunteers will be mandatory to proceed alongside the approval of local ethics committee (as needed).
Humans	All	Activities (or results produced) that could potentially be detrimental for the human participants involved (ex: stigmatization of vulnerable individuals/groups, negative socioeconomic consequences, etc.)	While preparing the activities, PARC researchers must carefully consider and identify potential risks for the involved participants (ex: identify and outline mitigation measures in the study protocol of the activity). Ethics approval should be obtained prior to any activity. If non-negligible risks can occur, contingent measures must be identified, defined and implemented during the activities. This information should be included in the information provided to volunteers to ensure informed consent
Humans	All	Volunteers wishing to withdraw their participation	PARC activities should be designed in a way that allows volunteers to withdraw their participation / inputs unless the data produced have been anonymized and cannot be linked to a specific individual

Human cells/tissues	WP4, WP5, WP6	Activities including the use of human cells and tissues	Human cells/tissues used in PARC activities must be in line with national and EU regulation, including EU directive 2004/23. In particular, the origin of cells / tissues / biological matrices used and or collected must be tracked and their collection must have the required authorisation. PARC organisation must also keep the records available
Human cells/tissues	WP4, WP5, WP6	Activities including the reuse of human cells and tissues previously obtained/collected for another purpose	Informed consent from the donor to secondary use of the material collected/obtained is mandatory. The donor must also be informed of how the material will be processed (storage, and disposal notably). If the initial consent is given for secondary uses within the framework of a given project PARC partners should check whether the new study falls within the scope of that consent.
Human cells/tissues	WP4	Use of human cells/tissues that comes from biobanks	Additional consent of the initial donor must be verified and obtained prior to any further use of materials stored in biobanks. If the biobanks initial consent form permit further use of the data, PARC partners should make sure that the data is either anonymised (Maintain a list with the minimum necessary data associated with the sample and irreversibly anonymize it) or (as much as possible) make sure that the individuals can give a new informed consent.
Use of personal data	All	Activities including the use and processing of personal data (including organisation of meetings and workshops, interviews, questionnaires, surveys, etc.)	The use of the personal data in the framework of PARC activities must comply with the national and EU legislations, in particular the EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).
Use of personal data	All	Activities including the use and processing of 'special categories of personal data' (of relevance for PARC, this notably includes the	PARC activities must comply with national and EU regulations, notably concerning the data-protection safeguards for the 'special categories of personal data' defined in the GDPR.

		biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person and data concerning health)	Wherever possible, the data will be anonymised or pseudonymised. If not feasible, this should be justified. PARC will make sure that all participants are aware of the objectives of the studies, and that they opt-in through detailed Informed Consent procedures.
Use of personal data	WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7,	Activities involving re-use of further processing of previously collected personal data.	Informed consent for the reuse / reprocessing of data is necessary in addition to the permission by the data owner / data manager. As much as possible, express consent should be obtained from the individuals. Further processing of data must meet the GDPR requirements
Use of animals	WP5	PARC activities will involve animal experimentation	PARC is committed to contribute to the 3Rs, notably with the development of NAMs, however, some activities will still require animal studies. Protocols for these studies will be set up to reduce the number of animals or refine the experimental protocol to avoid as much as possible any pain or discomfort for the animals. Beyond national and EU legislation which require authorization for animal experimentation, the use of animals within PARC activities will also have to be detailed and justified to the MB. Animal data from external studies used in PARC should be compliant with 3R and national legislation.
Involvement of non-EU countries	All	PARC partners include non-EU countries (ex: UK, Switzerland, etc.) that may not be subject to the same EU-wide standards and regulations. PARC will involve participants from non-EU countries	PARC activities that take place in non-EU countries must also be allowed in at least one EU member state. Non-EU countries participating in PARC should be treated as equal partners and enjoy equitable sharing of benefits
Involvement of non-EU countries	All	PARC will collect, produce and exchange materials (either from human or animal	If legally required, the transfer of genetic resources across borders, must obtain the necessary authorisation for the

		sources) from and to non-EU countries	transfer (ex: ethics approval, export license, Material Transfer Agreement, etc.). In addition, the collection / obtention of the material must be allowed in at least one EU member state
Involvement of non-EU countries	All	PARC will collect, produce and exchange data from and to non-EU countries	Likewise, in addition to meeting the requirements of GDPR, the data transfer and/or collection should also be in line with the national legislation of the non-EU country and approved by the competent local ethics commission and of the DPO.
Environment	WP4, WP5, WP6	PARC activities may involve use of substances or processes that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants	PARC activities must assess potential risks to the environment and identify countermeasures if pertinent. This requires the obtention of environmental and health and safety authorizations if applicable. Staff that can be exposed to harmful substances must be adequately informed and trained to deal with hazards relevant to the activity.
Artificial intelligence	WP6, WP7, WP9	PARC activities include the development and use of AI tools.	The development of AI tools must carefully consider how to remove possible bias for any uses that involves and/or have consequences on humans and/or other organisms. The use of AI tools must have human oversight and should be limited to support role, not decision-making.
Artificial intelligence	WP8	AI tools can be used in the development of safe and sustainable by design of chemicals. In these cases, the potential misuse of these AI tools for creating hazardous instead of safe chemicals should be examined and prevented.	Use of the tools developed should be monitored and preventive measures taken to avoid this type of misuse.
Artificial intelligence	WP8	Potential use of AI in combination with big	Specific care must be taken into account from the design phase

		data scraping of data about human participants could result in revealing the identity of such human participants	of all AI-powered tools to ensure that the anonymity of the data is safeguarded.
OTHER ETHICS CONCERNS IDENTIFIED			
Conflict of interest	All	PARC internal actors having conflict of interest that sways their decision-making.	PARC internal actors with significant operational decision-making role (currently, MB Principal Representatives and MB Principal Deputy) have to complete a Declaration of Interest (DoI) ⁶ and update it yearly or whenever relevant. This DoI is reviewed by the DEPB to identify potential conflict of interest and alert the coordinator and relevant decision-making bodies when necessary.
Conflict of interest	All	PARC external actors having conflict of interest that sways their advisory role	The contribution of PARC external actors in advisory bodies (ex: SF, IB) must be critically assessed by PARC actors and how the feedback has been taken up specified in relevant deliverables or PARC activities.
Conflict of interest	All	PARC actors or participating organisations receiving private funding from entities or individuals that may have financial interests in the outcome of a scientific project.	While receiving private funding is possible, these PARC actors and organisations have to disclose this interest link.
Intellectual Property Rights	All	Invention resulting from PARC activities with potential commercial use being unduly withheld by a PARC actor / participating organisation.	The rules regarding access rights and use of Background have been set-out in the PARC Consortium Agreement (Section 9 – Access Rights). In addition, the rules for ownership and use of results generated within PARC are also detailed in the Consortium Agreement (Section 8 – Results). Likewise, the Grant Agreement covers IPR in Article 16

⁶ Declaration of Interest form available as annex #2.

			'Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) — background and results — access rights and rights of use'.
Intellectual Property Rights	All	Non-authorized disclosure/use of information in PARC activities by a PARC actor / participating organisation.	The rules regarding confidential information and non-disclosure have been set-out in the PARC Consortium Agreement (Section 10 — Non disclosure of Information). It completes the provisions detailed in Article 13 of the Grant Agreement (Section 'Confidentiality and Security')

3. Ethics roles and responsibilities: ethics procedures

3.1 Overarching guideline

Duty to inform

During the preparation and implementation of their work, PARC participants are likely to encounter ethics challenges. To ensure that the T1.4 and the DEPB can adequately identify and monitor ethics issues (and how/if they have been addressed), PARC participants should specify and detail the issue encountered and (if relevant) how the issue had been addressed. Participants should also conserve all relevant documentation. This information will be instrumental to prepare the yearly ethics reports.

Several situations may be encountered depending on when the concern is identified:

Situation #1 : If the issue has been identified in advance and duly addressed before an actual issue appeared:

Participants should detail the issue identified in the yearly update of the project fiche or in the initial phase of the Project description and keep records of relevant documentation in case further information is requested by T1.4, the DEPB or by HaDEA. If the ethic issue is not linked to a specific project, please inform the PARC Coordination (parc@anses.fr) with the T1.4 co-leaders in CC (Philippe Marin - philippe.marin@ehesp.fr and Lucija Perharic - Lucija.Perharic@nijz.si).

Learning and sharing good practices within the PARC consortium will strengthen the fulfilment of ethic obligations and the overall quality of PARC research.

Situation #2 : If the issue has occurred unexpectedly, but has been addressed:

Participants should contact the PARC Coordination (parc@anses.fr) with the T1.4 co-leaders in CC (Philippe Marin - philippe.marin@ehesp.fr and Lucija Perharic - Lucija.Perharic@nijz.si). They should describe the

issue, detail how it has been addressed and provide all relevant documentation. T1.4 and the DEPB may request further information and/or follow-up if needed.

Participant should also include this information in the yearly project fiche update.

Situation #3: If the issue is pending and support / guidance to proceed is required:

Please describe the issue faced using the template in the annex and contact the PARC coordination email address (parc@anses.fr) with the T1.4 co-leaders in CC (Philippe Marin - philippe.marin@ehesp.fr and Lucija Perharic - Lucija.Perharic@nijz.si). The Task co-leaders and the WP co-leaders should also be informed of issues encountered.

The query will be forwarded to the PARC DEPB which will provide feedback as soon as possible.

In your notification you should include:

- The WP involved
- The project involved (if pertinent)
- The description of the ethic challenge encountered (add identified solutions under consideration if relevant)
- The type of feedback requested from Task 1.4 (ex: further information, guidance on how to proceed, validation of process, etc.)

When facing ethics challenges, it is PARC's participants' duty to seek approvals by the competent Ethics Committee and keep records.

All PARC participants are expected to respect the relevant EU and their national regulations which notably define when ethics approvals are mandatory and outline what records should be kept,

When participants identify possible ethics challenges in their activities and/or prepare activities that may lead toward ethics issues, they should first consult with their local/internal ethic board to assess whether the activity can proceed as it is (ex: if the risk is negligible), or if contingency measures should be implemented.

If pertinent the PARC DEPB can be consulted with the above-mentioned procedure.

The final storage of all relevant ethic documentation is the responsibility of the organisation/project managers. They should keep all required documentation and records and if requested, forward them to T1.4 co-leaders, the PARC CT and/or the DEPB.

Some documents may be requested and kept by the PARC CT.

To allow T1.4 co-leaders, the PARC CT and the DEPB to have an overview on the documents available and to ensure that all necessary documentation has been collected by PARC participants, a survey will be sent periodically by the CT. In this survey listing the necessary ethics documents, the participants will have to specify which documents have been obtained and justify should other documents be unavailable.

This documentation may be demanded to the PARC CT by the assessors of HaDEA during the reporting phase. Failure to provide the required ethics documents may make the activities ineligible for reimbursement by the European Commission.

3.2 Thematic guidelines

3.2.1. Human involvement and informed consent

Informed consent of human participants is crucial to ensure an ethical research. PARC activities must provide participants with all the necessary information needed to make an informed choice regarding their participation.

Informed Consent

To that end, PARC activities that involve human participants should provide them with at least the two following documents:

- **Information sheet**
- **Information consent form**

These documents should

- Be written in a language and in terms they can fully understand (adhering to the requirements of ethics approval legislation and ethics committees and the requirements of GDPR, see Art. 7, 12, 34);
- Describe the aims, methods and implications of the research, the nature of the participation and any benefits, risks or discomfort that might ensue;
- Explicitly state that participation is voluntary and that anyone has the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw their participation, samples or data at any time — without any consequences;
- State how biological samples and data will be collected, protected during the project and either destroyed or reused subsequently;
- State what procedures will be implemented in the event of unexpected or incidental findings (in particular, whether the participants have the right to know, or not to know, about any such findings if individual results are disclosed).

The Principal investigator (PI) or Project Manager (PM) or persons delegated to this task) must ensure that potential participants have fully understood the information and do not feel pressured or coerced into giving consent. Organisation implementing the activity must obtain and keep the informed consent forms and then notify the PI/PM by email.

The PI/PM then have to notify the CT once that the informed consent has duly be obtained by all implementing organisations via a form. Indeed, via this form they explicitly confirm that all the required documents concerning the ethics and data protection are available - saved as the local level — and may be requested by the PARC CT/DEPB/European Commission.

Participants must normally give their consent in writing (e.g. by signing the informed consent form and information sheets). For individuals who are unable to provide informed consent by themselves (ex: children), the consent of the legal representatives shall be obtained. If consent cannot be given in writing, for example because of illiteracy, non-written consent must be formally documented and independently witnessed.

Organisations implementing the activity are responsible to store and maintain the informed consent forms and should be able to provide it in a short notice if requested by T1.4, the PARC CT and/or the PARC DEPB.

The PI or PM should also have available relevant documents outlining the recruitment, inclusion and exclusion criteria of participants and informed consent procedures, as well as on unexpected findings policy.

In some cases, **copies of ethics approvals** (if required by law or practice) can also be mandatory.

PM/PI have to keep track and confirm that they have all the required documents concerning the ethics and data protection.

3.2.2 Use of human cells/tissues

PARC activities that involve the use of human cells and/or tissues must comply with all applicable international, EU and national law (in particular, EU Directive 2004/23 on standards for the donation, procurement, testing, processing, preservation, storage and distribution of human tissues and cells).

This notably means that PARC participants **must keep track of the origin of the cells and tissues** used, produced or collected. To that end, they must obtain:

- The **necessary accreditation/designation/authorisation/licensing** for using, producing or collecting the cells or tissues;
- The **Free and fully informed consent** of the donors.

Human cells/tissues used in PARC can only be obtained either:

- from commercial sources
- as part of PARC activities
- from another project, laboratory or institution
- from a biobank.

How the cells/tissues are obtained influences which documents must be kept by PARC participating organisations involved, and can be requested by the PM, PARC CT, DEPB or the European Commission. Indeed:

- if the human cells/tissues are obtained from commercial sources, involved organisations should keep copies of import licences (if relevant);
- if the human cells/tissues are obtained from PARC activities, involved organisations should keep copies of ethics approval, informed consent and information sheets (see subsection 'Human involvement and informed consent above);
- if the human cells/tissues are obtained from another project, laboratory or institution, the authorisation by primary owner of cells/tissues (including references to ethics approvals), copies of import licences (if relevant) and a statement from the primary laboratory/institution that informed consent has been obtained must be kept by the PARC participating organisation involved;

- if the human cells/tissues are obtained from a biobank, it is important to keep copies of import licences (if relevant) and a statement from the biobank that informed consent has been obtained.

In addition, if the activity uses human embryonic or foetal cells or tissues, the PI or PM must keep copies of ethics approval, the informed consent forms and information sheets as well as the registration certificates of the cell lines and project from the Human Pluripotent Stem Cell Registry (hPSCreg) or the European Union (if applicable).

3.2.3 Data use and processing

During the preparation and implementation of its activities, PARC will inevitably use and process data including sensitive data (ex: special categories of personal data as defined in the GDPR) which must be processed in accordance with certain principles and conditions that aim to limit the negative impact on the persons concerned and ensure fairness, transparency and accountability of the data processing, data quality and confidentiality.

The key legislation to take into account is the GDPR 2016/679. The GDPR is the branch of human rights protecting the rights of the data-subject thus supplementing the bioethical principles protecting the study participant. Further information to help researchers keep within the framework of the GDPR are available [here](#).

PARC also needs to be aligned with national Data Protection Laws of the countries where the data is collected, used and processed.

As far as possible and unless necessary, it is good practice to pseudonymise or anonymise the personal data produced and used in PARC have to be pseudonymised or anonymized (or exemptions duly justified) Indeed, this facilitate its use as it is not subject to the same level of care under the GDPR regulation.

3.2.3.1 Personal data:

Partners involved in PARC activities producing, using or processing personal data should make sure to keep informed consent forms and information sheets (if relevant), Data Management Plan (if relevant)⁷ and Data protection impact assessment (if relevant).

If it involves the processing of special categories of personal data (e.g. sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, genetic, biometric and health data, political opinion, religious or philosophical beliefs), then the PI or PM must also obtain the declaration confirming compliance with the laws of the country where the data were collected.

PARC activities involving profiling, systematic monitoring of individuals, or processing of large scale of special categories of data or intrusive methods of data processing (such as, surveillance, geolocation tracking etc.) must also provide the opinion of the data controller on the need for conducting data protection impact assessment under art 35 GDPR (if relevant).

⁷ PARC will develop its own Data Management Plan under WP7. However when data is collected and stored by the organisations involved in PARC, it is important to have available the Data Management Plan of respective organisations.

3.2.3.2 Data reuse:

For PARC activities involving further processing of previously collected personal data (including use of pre-existing data sets or sources, merging existing data sets), it is imperative for the PI or PM to obtain:

- Confirmation that the data controller has a lawful basis for the data processing and that the appropriate technical and organisational measures are in place to safeguard the rights of the data subjects
- Permission by the owner/manager of the data sets (e.g. social media databases) (if applicable).
- Informed Consent Forms + Information Sheets + other consent documents (if applicable)

3.2.4. Animal experimentation

The use of animal experimentation is a rising ethic concern for EU citizens.

PARC must ensure that the welfare of animal used in scientific procedures is ensured. Indeed, beyond the legal obligations relevant for animal experimentation (ex: Directive 2010/63/EU on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes) that must be respected by all PARC partners, in its activities, PARC is committed to support and implement the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement) principles.

This means that all PARC animal experimentation will have to be duly detailed and justified to the PARC Management Board via the completion and submission of an Information Memo.

For projects that relies on sub-contracting animal studies, extra caution is required and they must obtain the explicit approval from the Management Board. This must be achieved through the submission of a Decision Memo to the MB which prompts a formal approval vote.

Concretely projects looking to rely on animal experimentation will have to complete a Information/Decision Memo (template in annex) that will be sent for review (and approval for Decision Memo) to the Management Board (see process in the Fig. 2 below).

Fig. 2 – Validation of animal experimentation in PARC

Beyond this internal process, partners and projects involved in animal experimentation must obtain and conserve at least the following documents:

- copies of all **appropriate authorisations** for the supply of animals and the project experiments.
- copies of the **explanation sheet** explaining why it is necessary to come to animal studies in this specific case.
- copies of **training certificates/ personal licences** of the staff involved in animal experiments.

If the experimentation involves non-human primates (NHP), the PI/PM should also obtain the personal history file of NHP in line with article 31 of the Directive 2010/63.

In addition, if the animal(s) in question has been genetically modified, the PI/PM must have:

- copies of all appropriate authorisations for the supply of animals and the project experiments;
- copies of training certificates/ personal licences of the staff involved in animal experiments.

If they are cloned farm animal, the PI/PM have to provide an additional document:

- copies of authorisations for cloning (if required);

Furthermore, if the animal comes from an endangered species, then the PI/PM must have available:

- copies of authorisations for supply of endangered animal species (including CITES) and the project experiments;
- copies of training certificates/ personal licences of the staff involved in animal experiments.

3.2.5. Involvement of non-EU countries

PARC involves many partners (list available here on the PARC website) that comes from non EU-countries and close collaboration (including exchange of data and materials) are foreseen. Due to differences in regulations and ethics standards, it is very important that the activities in non-EU countries at least match the high ethical standards from EU (and national) regulations.

Indeed, it is a contractual obligation under Horizon Europe that activities carried out outside the EU must be allowed in at least one Member State. Compliance with the legal obligations of a non-EU country is not sufficient.

In addition, any use of local resources (especially animal and/or human tissue samples, genetic material, live animals, human remains, materials of historical value, endangered fauna or flora samples, fossils) must show respect for cultural traditions and share benefits (i.e. also benefit local participants and their communities, involve local stakeholders — as equal partners — and respond to local needs). In addition, if genetic resources are transferred across borders, it may be mandatory under the law of the provider country to obtain an authorisation for the transfer.

For all activities involving non-EU countries, PARC PI/PM must be careful to obtain:

- copies of ethics approvals and other authorisations or notifications (if required);

- confirmation that the activity could have been legally carried out in an EU country (for instance, an opinion from an appropriate ethics structure in an EU country).

The local partner should keep the documents and sends them to the PM/PARC CT/PARC DEP/ European Commission upon request.

In addition, if the activities plan to use local resources, PI/PM should also acquire documentation showing compliance with the **UN Convention on Biological Diversity** (e.g. access permit and benefit sharing agreement) for animal; plants and micro-organisms.

If it is planned to import any material (other than data) from a non EU-country into the EU / into another non-EU country or if it is planned to export any material from the EU to non-EU country, involved participants should make sure to have the copies of import/export licences/ Material Transfer Agreement (MTA).

Furthermore, if it is planned to export personal data (data transfer) from the EU to non-EU countries or import personal data from non EU-countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country, you should provide:

- confirmation that data transfers will be made in accordance with Chapter V of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 ;
- confirmation of compliance with the laws of the country in which the data was collected.

Finally, if the activity plan to send project teams to a non-EU country, a RA must be undertaken when sending project teams abroad and appropriate safety measures must be taken. If the situation in the visited country can put the individuals taking part in the activity at risk, visiting participants should make sure to have insurance coverage.

3.2.6. Environment, health and safety

PARC must be careful that its activities do not endanger the environment or the health and safety of the persons involved. While no major concerns are identified at this stage, PARC must remain cautious of and safeguard against unintended and unexpected consequences. Should major concerns be identified, associated to the use of hazardous chemicals for experimental studies or analytical activities, all partners using these chemicals will have to apply strictly the relevant safety procedures.

Indeed, in the framework of Chemical RA, PARC will have researcher teams monitoring the environment and teams implementing studies with hazardous materials which require to adhere strictly to safety procedures.

The PI/PM must make certain that they have obtained the relevant:

- **Environmental authorizations** (if applicable)
- **Health and safety authorisations** (if applicable)

This means that if PARC activities involves substances or processes (or technologies) that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants or to humans, including those performing the activity (during the implementation of the activity or further to the use of the results, as a possible impact), the PI/PM should ensure that safety measures are implemented, and should keep available:

- The safety classification of laboratory

- The host Institution safety procedures

The involved PARC partners should also make sure that their staff have adequate training in storing, handling and disposing of toxic chemicals substances. If new substances and/or formulations (e.g. nanomaterials) are developed, PM/PI must provide adequate RA.

For fieldwork, the PI/PM should establish and abide by recognised procedures to help keep teams and participants safe. This notably includes:

- keeping careful notes of all work engagements ensuring projects are adequately staffed
- using mobile phones to keep in touch with the home base
- conducting full RA of fieldwork sites
- formally notifying authorities of activities being conducted in an area
- carrying authorised identification
- preparation and training covering techniques for handling conflict, threats, abuse or compromising situations
- debriefing after fieldwork with an assessment of safety and
- reporting of health and safety incidents.

3.2.7. Artificial intelligence

AI is more and more prevalent in the daily life of EU citizens and introduce a new set of ethics challenges.

As PARC will develop AI-powered tools to support decision-making and risk monitoring, it is important to ensure that they are designed and developed in line with high ethical standards to prevent bias.

PARC activities that will involve the development, deployment and/or use of AI-based systems must prepare:

- **Detailed RA accompanied by a risk mitigation plan** (if relevant) covering the development, deployment and post-deployment phases.
- **Copies of ethics approvals** (if relevant)

If the AI-based system will be used by human participants, and it is designed to interact, replace or influence human decision-making processes (ex: e.g. issues affecting human life, health, well-being or human rights, or economic, social or political decisions), it is also important to have information sheets (and informed consent if relevant) outlining that participants are interacting with an AI system and informing them (in a language and terms understandable by all) about its abilities, limitations, risks and benefits.

4. Conclusion

As outlined in this deliverable, PARC acknowledges that its activities have significant ethical implications that must be taken into account in their design and implementation.

With this document, we intended to outline the ethics structure in PARC, identify potential ethics concerns and set out clear guidelines to accompany and support PARC partners in addressing those risks in line with the high ethical standards expected.

We nevertheless can expect to face unforeseen or rising ethics issues that are not (entirely) covered here. Therefore PARC intends to be active with its ethics practices and processes to match the learning experience and progress of the activities. To that end, this deliverable will be revisited in M42 (D1.13). Likewise, the ethic structure (T1.4, DEPB) and processes outlined here will be improved upon on a continuous basis.

Finally, we are aware of the expectations that PARC will bring chemical risk assessment and risk management forward and we believe that this should include relevant ethics practices and processes. Consequently, we will explore topics where we could leverage the scope and engagement of the partnership to improve upon common ethics processes (ex: pushing forward informed consent procedures, data use, AI and/or contributing to the development of NAMs, etc.).

References

General ethic information

- ‘How to complete your ethics self-assessment’ guidance from the European Commission, available online (https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/how-to-complete-your-ethics-self-assessment_en.pdf)
- ‘Identifying serious and complex ethics issues in EU-funded research’ guidance from the European Commission, available online (https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/guidelines-on-serious-and-complex-cases_he_en.pdf)
- ‘Ethics and data protection’ guidance from the European Commission, available online (https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf)
- ‘Ethics in Social Science and Humanities’ guidance from the European Commission, available online (https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-in-social-science-and-humanities_he_en.pdf)
- ‘European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity’, from ALLEA — ALL European Academies, available online (https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/european-code-of-conduct-for-research-integrity_horizon_en.pdf)
- HBM4EU Deliverable 1.5 ‘Legal and Ethics Policy Paper’, available online (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/mdocs-posts/hbm4eu-legal-and-ethics-policy-document/>)
- ‘Ethics for researchers — Facilitating Research Excellence in FP7’ from the European Commission, available online (https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/fp7/89888/ethics-for-researchers_en.pdf)

Human involvement and informed consent

- ‘Declaration of Helsinki - Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects’ from WMA — the World Medical Association, available online (<https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-helsinki-ethical-principles-for-medical-research-involving-human-subjects/>)
- ‘Oviedo Bioethics Convention - Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine’, from the Council of Europe, available online (<https://rm.coe.int/168007cf98>)

Use of human cells/tissues

- ‘Declaration of Taipei — Ethical considerations regarding health databases and biobanks’ from WMA — the World Medical Association, available online (<https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-taipei-on-ethical-considerations-regarding-health-databases-and-biobanks/>)
- ‘Directive 2004/23/EC - setting standards of quality and safety for the donation, procurement, testing, processing, preservation, storage and distribution of human tissues and cells’, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32004L0023>)
- ‘Directive 2006/17/EC - technical requirements for the donation, procurement and testing of human tissues and cells, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32006L0017>)
- ‘Directive 2006/86/EC - traceability requirements, notification of serious adverse reactions and events and certain technical requirements for the coding, processing, preservation, storage and distribution of human tissues and cells’ from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32006L0086>)
- ‘Directive 2015/565 - technical requirements for the coding of human tissues and cells’, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32015L0565>)
- ‘Directive 2015/566 - procedures for verifying the equivalent standards of quality and safety of imported tissues and cells’, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2015.093.01.0056.01.ENG)

Data use and processing

- ‘Regulation (EU) 2016/679 - protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR)’, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2016.119.01.0001.01.ENG)
- ‘Ethics and data protection’ guidance from the European Commission, available online (https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf)
- ‘Ethics and Data Protection Decision Tree’, from the European Commission, available online (<https://ec.europa.eu/assets/rtd/ethics-data-protection-decision-tree/index.html>)

- General guidances, recommendations and best practices issued by the EDPB - European Data Protection Board, available online (https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/general-guidance/guidelines-recommendations-best-practices_en)
- Overview of GDPR recommendations for researchers — from the UKRI, available online (<https://www.ukri.org/about-us/policies-standards-and-data/gdpr-and-research-an-overview-for-researchers/>)
- ‘Handbook on European data protection law - 2018 edition’, from FRA — European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, available online (<https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2018/handbook-european-data-protection-law-2018-edition>)
- ‘Directive 2002/58/EC - processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector’, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1399642277600&uri=CELEX:02002L0058-20091219>)
- ‘Directive 2006/24/EC - retention of data generated or processed in connection with the provision of publicly available electronic communications services or of public communications networks and amending Directive 2002/58/EC’, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1399642418437&uri=CELEX:32006L0024>)

Animal experimentation

- ‘Directive 2010/63/EU - protection of animals used for scientific purposes’, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online:

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1399643687417&uri=CELEX:32010L0063>)

- Documentation from the EU Reference Laboratory for alternatives to animal testing — EURL ECVAM, from the JRC - Joint Research Centre see website available online (https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/eu-reference-laboratory-alternatives-animal-testing-eurl-ecvam_en)

- ARRIVE guidelines (Animal Research: Reporting of In Vivo Experiments), see website available online (<https://arriveguidelines.org/>)

- Hooijmans C. et al.: A gold standard publication checklist to improve the quality of animal studies, to fully integrate the Three Rs, and to make a systematic review more feasible, 2010, ATLA 38

- Documentation from the National Centre for the Replacement Refinement & Reduction of Animals in Research — NC3Rs, see website available online (<https://www.nc3rs.org.uk/>)

Involvement of non-EU countries

- ‘Directive 2004/23/EC - setting standards of quality and safety for the donation, procurement, testing, processing, preservation, storage and distribution of human tissues and cells’, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32004L0023>)

- ‘Directive 2015/566 - procedures for verifying the equivalent standards of quality and safety of imported tissues and cells’, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2015.093.01.0056.01.ENG)

- ‘Nagoya Protocol - Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity’, from the Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity — United Nations, available online (<https://www.cbd.int/abs/>)
- ‘Regulation 511/2014 - Compliance measures for users from the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization in the Union’, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32014R0511>)

Environment, health and safety

- ‘Guidance on risk assessment at work’, from the European Commission (DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion), available online (<https://osha.europa.eu/de/legislation/guidelines/guidance-risk-assessment-work>).
- ‘EU Directive 2006/25/EC on the minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of the workers to risks arising from physical agents’, from the European Parliament and of the Council, available online (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=celex%3A32006L0025>).
- ‘Social Research Association Code of Practice for the Safety of Social Researchers’, from the SRA, available online (<https://the-sra.org.uk/common/Uploaded%20files/SRA-safety-code-of-practice.pdf>).
- European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA) website and resources on Occupational Health and Safety, available online (<https://osha.europa.eu/en/publications>).

Artificial Intelligence

- ‘Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI’, from the High-Level Expert Group on AI (AI HLEG), available online (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>)
- Regulatory framework proposal on artificial intelligence from the European Commission, available online (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>)
- ‘European Union Artificial Intelligence Act’, from the European Commission, available online (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021PC0206>).
- Resources from the European AI Alliance, see website available online (<https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance>)
- ‘Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence — ALTAI for self-assessment) from the AI HLEG, available online (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>).

See also the web-tool from the AI HLEG, available online (<https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/welcome-altai-portal#:~:text=The%20Assessment%20List%20for%20Trustworthy%20Artificial%20Intelligence%20%28ALTAI%29%2C,the%20trustworthiness%20of%20their%20AI%20systems%20under%20development>).

- ‘Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence’ guidance from the European Commission, available online (https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-by-design-and-ethics-of-use-approaches-for-artificial-intelligence_he_en.pdf)

- 'White Paper on Artificial Intelligence - A European approach to excellence and trust' from the European Commission, available online (https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-02/commission-white-paper-artificial-intelligence-feb2020_en.pdf)

Annexes

Annex 1 – PARC project ethics contact point

		Project acronym	Ethics referent
Started Y1	WP4	P4.1.1.2.a Y1 GenHBMSurvey VITO	liese.gilles@vito.be
		P4.1.1.4.a Y1 OccupFeasability TTL	tiina.santonen@ttl.fi
		P4.1.1.4.b Y1 SentinelSystem KULeuven	lode.godderis@kuleuven.be
		P4.1.1.4.c Y1 HealthCareSurvey TTL RUMC	paul.scheepers@radboudumc.nl
		P4.1.1.4.d Y1 OccupWaste ENSP TTL	tiina.santonen@ttl.fi
		P4.1.3.1.a Y1 DerivationofHBM-GVs UBA	Petra.apel@uba.de
		P4.1.3.3.a Y1 RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth SpF VITO	Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr
		P4.1.4.2.a Y1 DataAnalysisHBM4EU VITO	parc@vito.be
		P4.1.5.a Y1 SustainHBMSystem VITO	parc@vito.be
		P4.2.a Y1 ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey INERIS AU	kvo@envs.au.dk ; Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr
		P4.3.1.a Y1 T01-Concept Paper MU	elliott.price@recetox.muni.cz
		P4.3.1.b Y1 T02-QAQC WR	Hans.mol@wur.nl
		P4.3.1.c Y1 T03-EWStools SLU	Lutz.ahrens@slu.se
		P4.3.1.d Y1 T04-Data Processing Workflow EHESP	Arthur.david@ehesp.fr
	P4.3.2.a Y1 H01-Perinatal exposure INRAE	jean-philippe.antignac@inrae.fr	
	P4.3.3.a Y1 E01-Wastewater based epidemiology UFZ-UBATH	werner.brack@ufz.de	
	WP5	P5.1.1.a Y1 Toxins BfR UNIVIE	doris.marko@univie.ac.at ; jessica.dietrich@bfr.bund.de ; Henriqueta.Louro@insa.min-saude.pt
		P5.1.1.b Y1 BPA HumTox BfR	emanuela.testai@iss.it
		P5.1.2.a Y1 NaturalToxinsAqua UGent	Jana.asselman@ugent.be
		P5.1.2.b Y1 BPAalternatives BPI MU	ludek.blaha@recetox.muni.cz ; ondrej.adamovsky@recetox.muni.cz ; k.kyriakopoulou@bpi.gr
		P5.2.1.a Y1 NGTXCs INRAE	marc.audebert@inrae.fr ; Michael.Oelgeschlaeger@bfr.bund.de
		P5.2.1.b Y1 MD-EDC INRAE	daniel.zalko@inrae.fr
		P5.2.1.c Y1 EDThDisruption DTU	tesv@food.dtu.dk ; Tamara.Vanhaecke@vub.be
		P5.2.1.d Y1 Immunotox Inserm	robert.barouki@u-paris.fr ; etienne.blanc@u-paris.fr
		P5.2.1.e Y1 Neurotox UFZ IUF UU	tamara.tal@ufz.de ; ellen.fritsche@iuf-duesseldorf.de ; joelle.ruegg@ebc.uu.se
		P5.3.1.a Y1 SystemsToxicology UL-LACDR	b.water@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl
		P5.3.2.a Y1 AOPDevelopment Inserm	adelheid.soubry@kuleuven.be
		P5.3.4.a Y1 PBK Kinetics Fraunhofer	sylvia.escher@item.fraunhofer.de
P6.1.1.a Y1 HumanRelevance RIVM		Mirjam.Luijten@rivm.nl	

		P6.1.1.b Y1 IATA-ED UAntwerpen	dries.knapen@uantwerpen.be
		P6.1.1.c Y1 IATA GENTOX Sciensano	birgit.mertens@sciensano.be
		P6.1.1.d Y1 IATA STOT UL-LACDR	b.water@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl
		P6.2.1.a Y1 SourcetoDose VITO	Katleen.debrouwere@vito.be
		P6.2.1.b Y1 Aggregate Anses	amelie.crepet@anses.fr
		P6.2.2.a Y1 PBPK INERIS AUTH	spyrosk@auth.gr
		P6.2.3.a Y1 RealLifeMixtures RIVM	jacob.van.klaveren@rivm.nl
		P6.2.4.a Y1 HIADataAvailability VITO	jurgen.buekers@vito.be ; j.j.vlaanderen@uu.nl
		P6.2.4.b Y1 HIAMethod UU-IRAS	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl ; Jurgen.buekers@vito.be
		P6.2.4.c Y1 HIACaseStudies UU-IRAS	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl ; Jurgen.buekers@vito.be
		P6.2.4.d Y1 HIAIndicators VITO	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl ; Jurgen.buekers@vito.be
	WP6	P6.3.1.a Y1 SubstanceRA SU	marlene.agerstrand@aces.su.se
		P6.3.1.b Y1 EffectRA BPI	d.nikolopoulou@bpi.gr
		P6.3.2.a Y1 ToolsRA SU	marlene.agerstrand@aces.su.se
		P6.4.1.a Y1 OPREMIXCS1 BRUNEL UGot	thomas.backhaus@gu.se ; andreas.kortenkamp@brunel.ac.uk ; veronika.plichta@ages.at
		P6.4.1.b Y1 MONAMMIXCS2 UFZ	Wibke.busch@ufz.de ; veronika.plichta@ages.at
		P6.4.2.a Y1 LandscapingSurv UNIBAS	angela.bearth@hest.ethz.ch
		P6.4.2.b Y1 NGRApractice VKM NIPH	Gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no
		P6.4.2.c Y1 NAMAM UT	uko.maran@ut.ee
		P6.4.3.a Y1 SuProM MU	lisa.melymuk@recetox.muni.cz
		P6.4.4.a Y1 CRNCS1 KEMI	Johan.axelman@kemi.se
		P6.4.4.b Y1 PPPEXPCS2 SLU	Mikaela.Gonczi@slu.se
		P6.4.4.c Y1 PPPEFFCS3 UFZ	matthias.liess@ufz.de
		P6.4.4.d Y1 PPPBENCHCS4 UKOLD	schaefer-ralf@uni-landau.de
		P6.4.4.e Y1 PPPOSCS5 ISCIII	jtarazona@isciii.es
	WP7	P7.2.2.a Y1 chemicals-in-environment MU VITO	Richard.hulek@recetox.muni.cz
		P7.2.2.b Y1 HBMdatasets VITO	Jan.theunis@vito.be
		P7.3.3.a Y1 ALT-IST IISPV	vikas.kumar@urv.cat
Initiation Y2	WP4	P4.2.b Y2 Monitoringframe AU INERIS	kvo@envs.au.dk ; Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr
		P4.3.2.b Y2 H02-Occupational exposure INRS	sophie.ndaw@inrs.fr ; Radu.duca@Ins.etat.lu
		P4.3.3.b Y2 E02-Sentinel animals ONIRIS	ronan.cariou@oniris-nantes.fr
		P4.3.4.a Y2 F02-Food items exposure ANSES	julien.parinet@anses.fr

Annex 2 — PARC Declaration of Interest form

INDIVIDUAL DECLARATION OF INTEREST

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF RISKS FROM CHEMICALS (PARC)

INTRODUCTION

PARC is an EU-wide research and innovation programme to support EU and national chemical risk assessment and risk management bodies with new data, knowledge, methods, networks and skills to address current, emerging and novel chemical safety challenges. It will facilitate the transition to next generation risk assessment to better protect human health and the environment, in line with the Green Deal's zero-pollution ambition for a toxic free environment and will be an enabler for the EU Chemicals Strategy for sustainability.

Chemical risk and safety regulation is prevalent in the daily life of EU citizens but it is often perceived as obscure which provide fertile grounds for misconceptions and mistrust (ex: fear of corruption, connivance with private interests, etc.). It is thus important for PARC to be as upfront and transparent as possible to ensure that PARC meets the high standards of impartiality and objectivity expected by EU citizens in a public-public partnership. It is therefore crucial to put in place a process for preventing risks of conflicts of interest that could erode public trust and the uptake of PARC outputs. Members of the PARC Management Board (MB) will therefore be invited to complete a declaration of interest (DOI) in order to disclose any interests that may be considered as a source of conflict of interest (COI) that could potentially compromise their recommendations, opinions and decision-making within the scope of PARC's activities.

The PARC MB is composed of the WP co-leaders, the Coordinator and the Deputy Coordinator.

COI arises when the independence and impartiality of an individual may be affected or may reasonably be perceived by the public to be compromised by any substantial interests (financial, professional, familial, etc.) of relevance for PARC and that may influence his/her judgement.

For the matter of this DOI form, both current and past vested interests (Within the last five years) from the individual are to be disclosed.

Disclosing potential COI via this form does not automatically preclude individuals from participation and involvement in PARC MB activities. The interests disclosed in the forms will be reviewed by the two co-leaders of the T1.4 Ethics.

DEFINITIONS

"Link of interest" The notion of 'link of interest' covers the direct or indirect as well as past or present activities and interests (professional, familial and patrimonial) relevant to the mission entrusted to the individual in question.

"Conflict of interest" means any situation where an individual has an interest that may compromise or be reasonably perceived to compromise the individual's capacity to act independently in relation to the subject of the work performed in PARC.

"Close family member" means the individual's spouse, children and parents. "Spouse" includes a partner with whom the individual has a registered non marital regime. "Children" means the child(ren) the individual and the spouse have in common, the own child(ren) of the individual and the own child(ren) of the spouse.

"Legal entity" means any commercial business, industry association, consultancy, research institution or other enterprise whose funding is significantly derived from commercial sources. It also includes independent own commercial businesses, law offices, consultancies or similar.

"Body" means a governmental, international or non-profit organisation.

This declaration only addresses potential COI at the individual / personal level and not at the organisational level since organisations participating in PARC's higher management bodies are nominated by national authorities as PARC participants and they work at public institutions or private institutions with a public mandate.

This declaration should be updated at least once a year, and more frequently if there is a change in situation that warrants an update before the annual update.

INDIVIDUAL IDENTIFICATION

First name Surname _____

Organisation / Employer _____

Organisation
Country _____

Position / Mandate _____

Role in
PARC _____

Title _____

Please answer each questions with **YES** or **NO**.
If the answer to any of the question is **YES**, please describe any relevant interests by briefly providing context and circumstances in the associated table.

CATEGORIES

I – Employment and consultancy

Within the past 5 years, were you employed or have you had any other professional relationship with a natural or legal entity, or held any non-remunerated post in a legal entity or other body with an interest in the **regulatory field** of activity of PARC?

NO

YES (Fill the table below by adding additional lines as needed and provide detail regarding the nature of the activities)

Nature of activities/Role ⁸	Name of organisation or commercial entity	Time period	Description / context

II – Membership and affiliation

Within the past five years, have you participated in the internal decision-making of a legal entity or other body with an interest in the field of activity of PARC or have you participated in the works of a Scientific Advisory Body with voting rights on the outputs of that entity?⁹

NO

YES (Fill table below)

Nature of activities/Role	Name of organisation	Time period	Description / context

III – Research funding and support

⁸ For each element filled-in, please also mention the setting in which the activity was achieved: (i) Employment, (ii) Consultancy (incl. services as advisors), (iii) Non-remunerated post or (iv) legal representation.

⁹ This includes membership, affiliation and paid or unpaid position in governing bodies, scientific advisory bodies and other organisation that are of relevance for PARC.

Within the past 5 years, have you, your team or the entity to which you belong, directly received any support¹⁰ from a legal private entity?

NO

YES (Fill table below)

Nature of activities/Role	Name of organisation	Time period	Description / context

IV – Financial investments

Do you have current investments in a commercial entity with an interest in the **regulatory field** of activity of PARC, including holding of stocks and shares, stock options, equity, bonds, partnership interest in the capital of such undertaking, one of its subsidiaries or a company in the capital of which the commercial entity has a holding and which amounts to more than 10,000 EUR per commercial entity or entitling you to a voting right of 5% or more in such commercial entity?¹¹

NO

YES (Fill table below)

Investment name	Name of organisation or commercial entity	Description / context

V – Intellectual Property Rights

Do you have any intellectual property rights (e.g. patent, trademark, copyright or proprietary know-how) in the **regulatory field** of activity of PARC that might be affected by PARC's activities ?

NO

YES (Fill table below)

¹⁰ This include monetary research support (research funding, grants, collaborations, sponsorship, etc.) as well as non-monetary research support of significant value (above 1000 EUR) such as equipment, access to facilities, fellowships, paid travel costs, etc.

¹¹ You may exclude mutual funds, pension funds or similar investments that are broadly diversified and on which you exercise no control.

Intellectual property	Name of organisation or commercial entity	Description / context

VI – Other relevant information

Are there any other elements that could be seen as jeopardising your independence when working on PARC activities and management?

NO

YES (Provide details below)

VII – Interest of close family members

To your knowledge, do any of your close family members (parents, spouse / partner and children) hold any current interests (as specified above in the sections I-VII) in the regulatory field of activity of PARC which could be seen as undermining your independence and influencing your decision-making/advice?

NO

YES (Fill table below)

Section relevant for the interest of the close family member	Nature of activities/Role	Name of organisation	Description / context

DECLARATION ON HONOUR

I, the undersigned, _____ understand the definition of a COI and have filled the 'Declaration of Interest' form to the best of my knowledge. I also understand that this form is not an exhaustive list of interests and commit to updating my 'Declaration of Interest' annually or as soon as new or modified interest comes to my knowledge.

Date:

Signature